

TIME AND POLARIZATION RESOLVED ULTRASONIC MEASUREMENTS USING A LENSLESS LINE-FOCUS TRANSDUCER

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ABSTRACT

We have developed a transducer which allows the benefits of Line-Focus Beam (LFB) acoustic microscopy to be realized over large areas, using a conventional pulser-receiver. Experimental evidence is presented to show that the transducer is correctly modeled in detail by Green's function theory, and that all relevant wave speeds can also be predicted using a much simpler geometrical ray model. Data obtained by simply rotating the transducer a fixed distance above the specimen are presented using grey-scale plots which establish the ease with which anisotropy can be revealed. Finally, a grey scale plot of rotational-scan data recast in terms of velocity is shown to demonstrate the simultaneous detection of both surface and pseudo-surface waves in the same crystallographic orientation of a silicon specimen.

INTRODUCTION

The use of a high frequency (~200 MHz) line-focus ultrasonic transducer in a vertical-scanning reflection acoustic microscope system for quantitative materials characterization is well known [1,2]. The technique relies on the measurement of the reflected radio-frequency tone burst echo amplitude, V , as a function of amount of defocus, z , and analysis of the interference minima in the $V(z)$ curve to obtain various surface wave velocities. A line-focus transducer launches surface waves in a specific direction, perpendicular to the focusing line. This means that, unlike point-focus transducers, which launch omnidirectional surface waves, line-focus transducers can be used to study anisotropy. Numerous anisotropic velocity measurements in crystals have been reported by Kushibiki and Chubachi [2]. Techniques for measuring thin film elastic properties on crystal substrates have been reviewed by Achenbach, Kim and Lee [3].

Recently we have developed a 10 MHz center frequency line-focus transducer with a large aperture and

wide bandwidth [4]. Although its relatively low resonance frequency gives spatial resolution on the order of millimeters rather than micrometers, our transducer is capable of all the tasks performed by line-focus transducers operating beyond 100 MHz. Moreover, the wide bandwidth of our transducer makes the transducer well suited for pulse-mode operation, and allows multiple echos to be resolved in the time domain. Because the transducer does not have a lens, the theory to predict its response for probing a submerged solid in pulse/echo mode can be developed by integration of the known time-domain Green's function. We show later in this paper how theoretical and experimental results are consistent with the predictions of a geometrical ray model [4]. We also show experimental results in the form of orientation-dependent surface wave velocity plots, which can be obtained directly by rotating the transducer at a fixed distance over anisotropic samples.

A LENSLESS LINE-FOCUS TRANSDUCER

Our line-focus transducer is made of inexpensive PVDF film (DT-028k, 28 μm thick, 12 $\times$ 30 mm^2 , AMP Inc.). The transducer (Fig. 1) is made by taping the edges of the film onto a cylinder of a radius of 25.5 mm with the short edge parallel to the axis, and casting tungsten-loaded epoxy (2:1 by weight) on top of the film inside a rectangular aluminum tube. The tube has a flat top and a circular bottom which matches the curve of the cylinder, and is also taped on the cylinder during construction. After curing of the epoxy, the tapes are removed and the transducer top is covered with a rectangular plate fitted with a UHF connector at the center.

Constructed with an impedance-matched and heavily damped backing, the transducer has wide bandwidth and can generate a short pulse when excited by a conventional pulser (Panametrics 5052 PRX). Shown in Fig. 2 are the waveform

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** Product identification is included to provide a complete description. It does not imply endorsement by NIST.

Fig. 1 Sketch of a lensless line-focus PVDF transducer.

Fig. 2 (a) Echo waveform and (b) amplitude spectrum from a glass sample.

and frequency spectrum of the first echo from a glass plate placed at the focal point of the transducer, with water as the coupling medium. The receiver gain was set at 20 dB. A

digital oscilloscope, together with a desk top computer, was used to record and process the time waveform.

MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUE

Time-domain surface acoustic wave measurements were demonstrated first by Yamanaka using a wideband spherically focused transducer [5]. When the distance is reduced between a sample and a transducer generating an impulsive converging beam, i.e. when the beam is defocused, multiple echoes appear after the direct reflected echo (Fig. 3). The arrival times of these echoes, t_D , t_L and t_R respectively, can be determined in relation to the initiation of the electrical pulsed source. Based upon a simple ray theory model, the velocity, C_R , of the leaky surface wave can be derived as

$$C_R = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1/(C_f * m) - 1/(4 * m^2)}} \quad (1)$$

where C_f is the wave velocity of the fluid, $m = z/\Delta t$, z is the amount of defocus distance, and $\Delta t = t_R - t_D$. The velocity C_L of the leaky longitudinal wave can also be similarly computed with the arrival time t_R replaced by t_L . Furthermore, z and C_f are related by

$$z = r - C_f * t_D / 2 \quad (2)$$

where r is the focal length of the transducer.

Fig. 3 Typical waveform obtained by defocusing a distance of 5.5 mm on a flat glass target. D: direct center-reflected wave. L: leaky longitudinal wave. R: Rayleigh wave. Arrows indicate their arrival time t with subscript D, L, and R.

In other words, only two of the three parameters z , r , and C_f need be known for a particular experiment. Since both the focal length and the wave speed of water can be

determined precisely and independently, the use of Eq. (2) to calculate z requires only the measurement of time. This fact, an advantage over the $V(z)$ measurement, has been clearly pointed out by Yamanaka[5].

THEORY AND NUMERICAL SIMULATION

Since our transducer does not have a lens, and the curved front surface of the transducer is the uniform active element which generates and detects the ultrasound, we can model the response of the transducer by superposition which involves integrations of the time domain Green's function of a liquid/solid interface over the transducer surface twice, once for transmission and once for reception.

The Green's function of a liquid/solid interface represents the transient pressure at any point in the liquid due to a sudden expansion at another point in the liquid near the planar solid. This Green's function has been derived and described in detail in the geophysics literature [6,7,8,9]. We have developed a simplified, easily programmed, efficient algorithm [10] for the Green's function $G(d,h,t)$, where d is the source-detector distance projected onto the surface, h is the sum of the perpendicular distances from source and detector to the surface, and t is time.

To model the lensless transducer with a concave front face of radius r , and chord length a , two surface integrals of the basic Green's function are required. However, the dimensions of the numerical integration can be reduced from four to two by invoking symmetry. The resulting transducer response function [11] can be written as

$$H(t,z) = r^2 \int_{-\alpha}^{\alpha} \int_{-\alpha}^{\alpha} G(d/h, t/(c_f h)) d\theta_0 d\theta \quad (3)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} d &= r |\sin\theta_0 - \sin\theta| \\ h &= r |\cos\theta_0 + \cos\theta| + 2z \\ \alpha &= \sin^{-1}(a/r). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

These numerical integrations can be carried out on a personal computer, although some computations may take hours to achieve reasonable accuracy. The detected pulse-echo waveform, $V(t,z)$, can be simulated by convolution of the transducer response function with a source waveform, $S(t)$, as

$$V(t,z) = \int_0^t \partial_{\tau} \partial_{\tau} H(z,\tau) S(t-\tau) d\tau. \quad (6)$$

(The two partial time derivatives are needed in Eq. (5) because the source-time function for the Green's function originally derived is a parabolic ramp function.) The source waveform, $S(t)$ can be obtained by solving Eq. (5) at the focal point ($z=0$) using an experimentally recorded $V(t,0)$ waveform and a computed $H(t,0)$ curve.

COMPARISON BETWEEN THEORY AND EXPERIMENT

Shown in Fig. 4 is a theoretically simulated waveform for the test conditions applicable to the experimental waveform shown in Fig. 3. The test sample was a glass plate with the following properties: $C_L=5.55$ km/s, $C_S=3.39$ km/s, $\rho=2200$ kg/m³. The distance between transducer and sample was 20 mm, since the transducer focal length is 25.5 mm, we have $z=5.5$ mm. The simulation is a numerical convolution of the transducer response function $H(t,z)$ with a source function, $S(t)$, obtained by deconvolution of the recorded echo waveform $V(t,0)$ (shown in Fig. 2a) received when the sample is at the focal point, with a theoretically computed $H(t,0)$. By comparing the shapes and arrival times of the features designated D, L, and R in the two figures, one can see that the experimental results and the theoretical predictions agree well.

Fig. 4 Simulated waveform based on Green's function theory. Same test condition as that of Fig. 3.

Shown in Fig. 5 are (a) experimentally scanned and (b) numerically computed $V(t,z)$ plots with the voltage plotted as a relative grey scale. The grey scale range has been adjusted to emphasize the low amplitude ripples. The features designated L and R on both plots clearly confirm the linear relationship between z and t for the arrival of leaky longitudinal waves and Rayleigh waves. This relationship is consistent with the simple ray model [4] mentioned earlier. By examining the feature R, one can see that the amplitude of the Rayleigh wave decreases as the path length increases with larger z , and that the pulse duration increases.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5 Grey scale plots of $V(t,z)$ scan over a glass sample. (a) experimental result. (b) theoretical simulation based on the Green's function.

APPLICATION TO ORIENTATION DEPENDENT VELOCITY MEASUREMENTS

By holding z constant and varying the angle β between the leaky surface wave propagation vector and an arbitrary vector in the plane of the surface of a sample, a line-

focus transducer can be used to determine the orientation dependence of the surface wave velocity due to anisotropy. Data from this experiment were stored in the form of a matrix of elements v_{ij} where v is the transducer output voltage at time t_i for transducer rotation angle β_j , and uniform increments of $0.004 \mu\text{s}$ and 2 degrees were maintained for t_i and β_j , respectively.

The $V(t,\beta)$ plot for leaky surface waves in the (001) plane of a silicon crystal is shown in Fig. 6. In addition to illustrating the ease with which anisotropic effects can be revealed using a line-focus transducer, this plot provides an indication of the spatial distribution of the elastic properties of the specimen. The appearance of the features marked R and Ps is consistent with theoretical predictions [12] for the arrivals of leaky surface waves (R) and pseudo-surface waves (Ps) in the [100] and [110] directions, respectively. We note that the detection of both types of surface wave in the same crystal orientation has not been achieved using acoustic microscopes of conventional design [3].

Fig. 6 Grey scale plot of $V(t,\beta)$ in the (001) plane of silicon.

Data from this type of experiment is easily recast in terms of wave velocity ($V(C,\beta)$), rather than wave arrival time ($V(t,\beta)$). With each value of t_i measured with respect to t_D , the arrival time of the direct reflected wave, Eq. 1 may be generalized to

$$C_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{t_i/(C_f * z) - t_i^2/(4 * z^2)}} \quad (6)$$

and used to calculate a velocity for each value of t_r . Clearly the mapping from time to velocity is nonlinear, and yields impractically large velocity for very small values of t_r . In Fig. 7, we show the result of applying this process to data from another rotational scan in the (001) plane of a silicon specimen.

By comparing Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, one can see that the $V(C,\beta)$ plot provides better definition of the features marked X in Fig. 7, which closely resemble theoretically predicted [3] horizontally polarized bulk transverse waves in the (001) plane of silicon.

Fig. 7 Grey scale plot of velocity versus orientation on the (001) silicon crystal plane.

CONCLUSION

The line-focus transducer is simple to make with readily available parts and can be operated with conventional ultrasonic instruments. Its wide bandwidth makes the transducer well suited to operate in transient pulse/echo mode, which, for a given percentage of measurement error, is much easier to use than the high-frequency equipment needed for conventional microscopy. For all experimental geometries considered thus far [11], both Green's function theory and a

simpler geometric ray model have been found to give very accurate predictions of transducer performance. We have shown that this transducer is easily used to detect anisotropy, and that the simultaneous detection of both surface and pseudo-surface waves in the same crystallographic plane of silicon can be done with our transducer.

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